

The background of the cover is a photograph of a meeting. In the foreground, a woman with dark hair is looking towards the right, holding a black pen. Behind her, a man is also looking in the same direction. In the background, another man is visible, resting his chin on his hand. They appear to be in a meeting room with a whiteboard and a screen displaying a blue and white graphic. The image has a slight motion blur effect, particularly in the lower half.

The Generations & Gender Programme: Technical Guidelines

Version 4.0

Generations and Gender Programme

Technical Guidelines

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Preface

These Technical Guidelines aim to provide the fieldwork specifications and requirements for countries that are planning to conduct the Generations and Gender Survey (GGS). The document outlines the responsibilities and timeline regarding the implementation of the GGS at all stages of fieldwork. The document is primarily targeted at national coordinators and research vendors contracted by the national teams.

This new version incorporates updates and revisions, especially regarding the web implementation of the GGS. It is also more condensed and aims to provide the general overview of the implementation of the GGS. The document was also prepared with inputs from partners of the Generations and Gender Programme (GGP) and other experts in the field.

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Terminology and abbreviations

- **AAPOR:** American Association for Public Opinion Research.
- **Baseline questionnaire:** Questionnaire used for the first wave of data collection.
- **Blaise:** Main survey software used to collect the data.
- **CAPI:** Computer Assisted Personal Interview
- **CATI:** Computer Assisted Telephone Interview.
- **CAWI:** Computer Assisted Web Interview.
- **DDI:** Data Documentation Initiative: International standard for describing the data produced by surveys and other observational methods in the social, behavioural, economic, and health sciences.
- **F2F:** Face-to-face.
- **FFS:** Family and Fertility Survey
- **Follow-up questionnaires:** Questionnaires for the second and third waves to capture longitudinal prospective changes in people's lives.
- **GDPR:** General Data Protection Regulation.
- **GGP Central Coordination Team (GGP CCT):** Headquarter of the GGP located at the Netherlands Interdisciplinary Demographic Institute, plus the GGP nodes located in France at the French Institute for Demographic Studies (INED) and in Germany at the Federal Institute for Population Research (BiB).
- **GGP:** Generations and Gender Programme: Research infrastructure as a whole.
- **GGS:** Generations and Gender Survey: Main instrument (survey) of the GGP.
- **GGS-I:** First round of data collection carried out during the period 2005-12; it included three panel waves of data collection (three years apart).
- **GGS-II:** Second round of data collection that started in 2017 with fresh samples in all countries and a revised questionnaire; the plan is also to have three panel waves (three years apart).
- **KNAW:** Koninklijke Nederlandse Akademie van Wetenschappen (Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences).
- **National coordinator and national teams:** People involved in the implementation of the survey in their country, together with the GGP CCT.
- **NIDI:** Netherlands Interdisciplinary Demographic Institute.
- **SHARE:** Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe.
- **Survey population:** population actually covered by the frame and surveyed.
- **Target population:** Population for which information is desired.
- **TranslationCTRL (formerly TMT, Translation Management Tool):** Tool that allows countries to translate the questionnaire.
- **UNECE:** United Nations Economic Commission for Europe.

Brief overview of the GGS

These guidelines outline the standards and requirements for data collection and preparation that must be adhered to by each country. The GGS is a cross-national longitudinal survey that provides open access data to researchers on topics including partnerships, fertility, work-life balance, gender relations, transition to adulthood, intergenerational exchanges, care and later life. The GGS is the central part of the Generations and Gender Programme (GGP; <https://www.ggp-i.org>), a Social Science Research Infrastructure initiated in 2000. Since 2009 it has been coordinated by the Netherlands Interdisciplinary Demographic Institute (NIDI), a part of the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences (KNAW). The Fertility and Families Survey (FFS) is the predecessor of the GGS and was conducted in the 1990s in 23 Member States of the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE). The GGS incorporates several innovations introduced in the FFS, but extended the age coverage to 18–79 in addition to strengthening the gender dimension and the relationship between generations as key components to understand contemporary life-course and family dynamics.

The key features that characterise the GGS are:

- longitudinal design with 3-year intervals between waves;
- fertility and partnership histories;
- relation between men and women;
- relations between generations.

The GGS is designed as a panel with 3-year intervals between each wave of data collection. This means that data is collected from the same respondents at different points in time. The GGS questionnaire covers a wide range of topics and focuses on fertility and partnership histories, gender relations, division of housework, work-family balance, transition to adulthood, intergenerational exchanges, economic activity, retirement, health and well-being (see Table 1 below). The GGS adopts a life course approach and collects both retrospective (fertility, family formation and dissolution) and prospective information (intentions to have children, intentions of union formation, and further prospective information through its panel design). The selection of the themes included in the questionnaire follow theoretically grounded criteria (Vikat et al., 2007).

The GGP has a set of online products available, including data documentation¹ that covers core and national questionnaires, codebooks, sampling information and country-specific documentation. An important online resource is the online browsing platform *Colectica*² that provides direct access to GGS data and metadata, allowing also for visualising simple descriptive statistics. The codebooks contain useful information on variable coding and country specificities. It is also possible to browse online and download the Contextual Database³, which gives access to cross-national contextual data (demographic, socio-economic and policy indicators).

The GGS has been extensively used across multiple scientific disciplines. The GGP website includes a list of hundreds of scientific publications based on GGS data. A selection of technical papers is also

¹ <http://www.ggp-i.org/data/methodology>.

² <https://ggp.colectica.org>

³ <http://www.ggp-i.org/data/ggp-contextual-database>

available covering technical aspects of the GGS: attrition, sampling, fieldwork methods, response rates, non-response, among other issues.

Table 1 | Information collected in the GGS

Questionnaire modules	Examples
Demographics	Sex; age; education; dwelling unit; building, occupancy; satisfaction with the accommodation.
Life Histories	Current partner; complete partnership history by month; intentions of union formation; consolidated children information; step children; complete childbearing history by month; total number of children.
Fertility	Ever had sexual intercourse; current pregnancy; fecundity; intentions to have children.
Household Decisions	Household roster; household organisation; decision-making; help and support; childcare; child alimony/ maintenance; partner alimony.
Generations	Questions about biological parents; brothers, sisters, grandparents; grandchildren; parental home during childhood; intentions to start living separately from parents; care and support.
Well-Being	Health in general; height and weight; locus of control; well-being; loneliness; depression.
Work	Current activity status; additional job or business; working conditions and availability of reconciliation policies; partners working status and conditions.
Income	Income from employment and other sources; total household income.
Attitudes	Religiosity; attitudes about interpersonal trust; attitudes about marriage; attitudes about gender.
Report	For CAP: Others present during interview; interruptions; interview quality.

One central element of the GGS and its contribution is cross-national comparability. Current rapid changes in society are hard to detect and interpret but are best understood from a cross-national perspective. In turn, this can only be done with cross-national comparable instruments which is why it is so important that national teams and GGP CCT adhere to these guidelines. In order to produce the greatest possible insights, scientists, stakeholders and policy-makers benefit immensely from access to data collected with a cross-national comparative design in which the indicators of interest are standardised and measured similarly across countries. High quality research necessitates standardisation and comparability.

These guidelines outline the responsibilities and timeline regarding the fieldwork implementation of the GGS. The objective is to ensure that high quality data is collected in a comparable way across the participating countries. The document starts by providing an overview of the timeline of activities and distribution of these tasks. The initial sections focus on the planning phase, which includes contact with the GGP CCT, formation of the national team, funding applications, tendering process, translation and signing agreements. Subsequently, the focus is on the preparatory phase activities, including pre-testing, interviewer training and sampling. Finally, the last sections focus on the fieldwork, data protection, consent and linkage, data archiving, reporting and panel maintenance.

1. OVERVIEW OF DATA COLLECTION STEPS AND SURVEY REQUIREMENTS

1.1. Timeline & Tasks

In this section we provide an overview of the activities required before, during and after the fieldwork for the initial wave of the GGS. In Table 2 (below), we give an approximation of the timing of the tasks at each stage, as well as an indication of who will be mainly responsible for the task. This is to provide a more concrete mapping of the activities to help national teams plan the implementation of the GGS. In some national contexts, it can be that some of these activities take longer or shorter than what is indicated in Table 2 depending on a number of factors. For example, we indicate two months for the sample design but sampling strongly depends on the available sampling frames in the country and therefore the duration of this stage can vary strongly. Similarly, the duration of the tendering process can deviate from what is indicated in the timeline depending, for example, on delays in receiving the bids.

The GGP CCT works closely with national teams to plan and execute the fieldwork using advanced software and survey tools. In addition to fieldwork activities, national teams are encouraged to plan and budget other documentation and communication activities to raise awareness of the survey and disseminate its findings.

The whole cycle of the fieldwork processes can be summarised in four main phases: planning, preparation, fieldwork and monitoring, and data processing and archiving. Each phase is briefly described below.

- **Phase 1: Planning.** The early stages of the project consist of five main steps: establishing contact with the GGP CCT; forming the national team (we recommend a consortium of different stakeholders); planning activities in line with the timeline; preparation of the budget and fundraising activities; submitting Service and Data Agreements.
- **Phase 2: Preparation.** The next steps concern the pre-fieldwork phase. At this stage, the national team prepares and finalises the tendering process (if applicable) with a decision on the organisation that will conduct fieldwork; translates the questionnaire using the TranslationCTRL; conducts the pre-testing of the translated questionnaire; establishes a sampling strategy and draws the sample, prepares and sends the invitation letters (mail-out or SMS), and undertakes interviewer training (in case of CAPI). The GGP CCT finalises technical preparations and makes any adjustments necessary in line with the results of the pre-testing. Moreover, it is important for the national team to consider organising awareness events and publicity to increase the public interest in the survey.
- **Phase 3: Fieldwork and monitoring.** The monitoring of the fieldwork operations helps to identify any potential issues during fieldwork, allowing for corrective measures and leading to improvements in data quality and timely release of the data. During the fieldwork, the GGP CCT supports national teams in the monitoring of the data collection. It reports regularly on the process.

- **Phase 4: Data processing, documentation, archiving and dissemination.** The GGP CCT will be mainly responsible for data processing – transforming the raw data collected into a ‘clean’ format so that it can be used for analysis. Additional post-fieldwork activities where the GGP CCT will be involved include the preparation of data documentation and data release. The national team will also possibly organise an event (or events) for dissemination of the GGP and to engage potential GGS data users and other stakeholders in the country.

Table 2 | Timeline (duration in months)

1.2. Checklist of Tasks for the National Team

Phase 1: Planning

- Establish contact with GGP CCT
- Apply for and secure the funding
- Submit signed Statement of Intent
- Identify the sampling frame (in collaboration with GGP CCT)
- Submit signed Service Agreement
- Submit signed Data Agreement
- Obtain ethics approval (if applicable)
- Plan the contact strategy and sample management

Phase 2: Preparation

- Translate the survey in the TranslationCTRL
- Submit Sampling and Fieldwork Design Form
- Draw the sample
- Conduct Interviewer Training (in case of CAPI)
- Conduct pre-testing (in all languages, if applicable)
- Prepare and send invitation letters

Phase 3: Fieldwork and Monitoring

- Monitor collection progress
- Manage and send reminders

Phase 4: Data processing, documentation, archiving and dissemination

- Deliver metadata and data for weighting and documentation purposes
- Deliver depersonalised contact data
- Submit panel maintenance strategy
- Organise an event (or events) to disseminate and engage potential GGS data users (optional)

1.3. Survey Requirements

In order to preserve the cross-national comparability of the survey, all countries are asked to adhere to the following guidelines.

Full survey

- Participation in the GGS is expected to involve: running the baseline questionnaire and at least one follow-up three years later (ideally two follow-ups).
- Full adherence to the questionnaires. Modifications of the questionnaires are not allowed unless they are imperatives (e.g. education level, income groups). Any other modification is only allowed in exceptional cases and has to be agreed upon by the GGP CCT. However, the addition of a few country-specific questions is allowed.
- Use of the TranslationCRTL to document the translation process.
- Use of the pre-coded Blaise questionnaire.
- The sample has to be nationally representative.
- The target population is aged 18–79 (if a country has a pre-existing ageing survey, this can be reduced to 18–59).
- The target net sample is 10,000 (for 18–79) or 7,000 (for 18–59).
- Additional over-sampling for specific groups is allowed (it has to be discussed with GGP CCT).
- The survey should ideally be carried out in mixed mode. Our preference is for CAWI and CAPI. Countries can also opt for CAWI only but only if sufficient measures and financial incentives are offered to reach good response rates and data representativity.
- National teams are responsible for sampling management.
- National teams are responsible for panel maintenance strategy.
- National teams are required to pay the standard GGS fee to cover a part of the support provided by the GGP CCT.

Pilot survey

Countries may opt to do a pilot survey prior to the full survey. The requirements are the same as above, but the sample size is smaller, ideally 1000 to 2000 people (net). In some cases, a pilot survey can be used to test the feasibility of a web survey, and/or the right incentive structure for the survey. It can also be used as a feasibility and demonstration study to help raise further funding.

2. PLANNING

2.1. Forming a National Team

When there is an institution or group of institutions interested in joining the GGP, the first step is to contact our GGP CCT. Although a single institution may field the GGS in their country, we strongly recommend forming a broad national consortium including key stakeholders involved in population studies, statistics and relevant ministries. The consortium should have a clearly defined representative – the national coordinator.

Among the initial considerations for forming the national team, it is important to keep in mind all the stages of the study. Before fieldwork starts, national teams must devote a significant amount of time to the preparatory and planning work, including funding applications. National teams are asked to keep the GGP CCT fully informed regarding crucial elements such as who are the (potential) funders; preliminary budget; partners included in the proposal; foreseen fieldwork dates; targeted population; additional deliverables (e.g., reporting, conferences, training) upcoming deadlines for the selected calls; amount of funding provided and when the results of the applications will be made available. In turn, the GGP CCT can assess whether there are any additional sources of financing which the national team is unaware of, particularly at the international level.

It is the responsibility of national teams to identify possible sources of national and regional funding. However, the GGP CCT can provide support in the preparation and submission of the funding application including building the political and scientific case.

It is expected that the national coordinator and fieldwork coordinator(s) become the main contact persons liaising directly with the GGP CCT. Each national team should appoint and finance its coordinators and team. In addition, the national team should have a clear idea about who will be responsible for preparing the tendering process, translating the questionnaire, sample design and accompanying the pre-test phase. For the data collection to proceed in line with the timeline above it is crucial that the national team communicates any problems as soon as possible to the GGP CCT. As mentioned, it is important that the national team also plans and prepares any publicity or awareness events in a timely manner.

2.2. Funding Applications and Survey Plans

The next step in terms of the planning stage involves acquiring funding for the project. This is the responsibility of the national team. However, we encourage teams to contact the GGP CCT for assistance including to properly budget for the project and to have a realistic timeline. It is recommended that you file with the GGP a survey plan which includes the following points:

- To whom has the funding proposal been submitted
- When is the outcome expected
- Foreseen fieldwork dates
- Targeted population
- Partners included in the proposal
- Preliminary budget

- Are there planned deliverables which are not associated with fieldwork (e.g. reporting, conferences, training)

These details will be very important for the GGP CCT to be able to program all the work that needs to be completed at all stages of the project. It is also important to keep in mind that funding applications can require a significant amount of time to prepare and, in some contexts, the results of the funding applications can take some time to be released.

2.3. Service and Data Agreements

Before fieldwork commences, it is essential that the fieldwork and data arrangements are formalised. To do this there are two agreements which need to be signed by the national team: Service Agreement and Data Agreement. Fieldwork will not be allowed to start until both of these agreements are signed.

Service Agreement

This agreement defines the roles and responsibilities of all parties involved in the implementation of the GGP. It explains the roles and responsibilities of the national partners involved and those of the GGP team at NIDI. It helps clarify who is responsible for what component of fieldwork and can be amended to reflect national contexts. Typically, the Service Agreement is signed by the director of the GGP, the director of NIDI and the national team. This agreement has to be signed before further work can start. The Service Agreement also includes information about a service fee associated with carrying out the GGS which is to be paid by the national team to the GGP CCT.

Data Agreement

This document establishes the responsibilities regarding data management, archiving, dissemination and use of the GGS microdata. The Data Agreement is between the GGP represented by NIDI and the national data provider (organisation or institution in charge of the microdata set of a national GGS) and covers the fieldwork process as well as the data provision to researchers through a registration process. The Data Agreement also regulates relevant data protection issues and outlines the requirements for potential users who wish to apply for data use (Terms of Acceptable Usage).

2.4. Sampling Requirements

Given that the GGS is an international survey intended for international comparison which has the potential to impact government policy with its findings, it is crucial to exercise care when designing the sample. In order to allow for inter-country and time dependent intra-country comparison it is necessary that **probability sampling** is used. It is essential that, in each participating country, the survey agency responsible for the sample design and implementation is a reputable institution that is willing and able to conform to the GGS Technical Guidelines.

A sampling expert within each national team will ultimately define which sample design is most appropriate for the GGS given the most suitable sampling frame and the method and cost of survey collection. Each country team will be asked to fill in the online form prepared by the GGP CCT as part of the process of approval of the sample and fieldwork design in each country. The GGP CCT will review the information provided and discuss the best solution in close collaboration with the national team.

We recommend that the following guidelines be used when selecting a sampling frame and sample design:

Target population

The target population is the resident non-institutionalised population within the specified age range at the time of wave 1.

GGG survey population: may exclude up to 5% of the target population

Often, exclusions are due to frame limitations or practical constraints – such as eliminating remote regions where survey collection would be prohibitively expensive. To facilitate international comparisons, we recommend that each country minimises exclusions from the target population as much as possible. Any country that excludes more than 5% of the target population must provide valid reasons for the proposed exclusions to the GGP CCT.

Over-sampling of subpopulations

Countries may over-sample targeted sub-populations. There are several reasons why a country would want to over-sample sub-groups, for example, past studies of non-response or an interest in a particular sub-population. We recommend that if a country over-samples some sub-populations, it should be reflected in the design weights in order to ensure unbiased estimates of the population.

Guidelines for response rate

It is recommended that the target response rate for GGS is at least 60% for F2F and 30% for CAWI (AAPOR RR2⁴). These numbers are challenging in some survey contexts and where this is the case, national teams should discuss mitigation strategies with the GGP CCT.

We do not recommend replacing non-respondents with other respondents. Measures for increasing response rates include well-written and formatted invitation letters, websites and other channels of communication offering information on the survey, incentives, training interviewers in obtaining cooperation and multiple contact attempts by interviewers, among other measures.

2.5. Design Requirements

Choosing the data collection mode

Data collection in the GGP can be conducted via F2F interviews (CAPI) or online (CAWI). These technical guidelines apply to both forms of data collection, but the GGP has adopted an additional set of guidelines on how online data collection should be conducted:

⁴ <https://aapor.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/Standard-Definitions20169theditionfinal.pdf>.

- National teams must get approval from the GGP CCT regarding their primary mode of data collection.
- Typically, the GGP only allows for an online survey as the primary mode of data collection in instances where an individual-level sampling frame is available or when a contact protocol has been piloted which demonstrates sufficient response rates and data quality (as determined by the GGP CCT).
- If the primary mode of data collection is online, incentives should ideally include both an unconditional and conditional component. These incentives should be considerably higher than standard face to face incentive rates.
- If the primary mode of data collection is online, re-contact rates between waves and panel maintenance activities must be greatly intensified and closely monitored.

2.6. Technical Requirements (CAPI Mode)

The fieldwork organisation in each country will need to ensure that it can and will comply with the following minimum technical requirements:

Blaise provides apps to be pushed to iOS/Android devices, available via the App Store or Google Play Store. While Blaise is meant to work on a wide variety of technologies ranging from handhelds with small screen sizes to very large browser screens, GGP CCT recommends using Android tablets for the best user experience. Surveys or specific cases can be uploaded to an app. The survey can be connected (Client-Server) or disconnected (stand-alone). In disconnected mode, the data will be stored (encrypted) on the device until the interviewer connects again and uploads the data.

In terms of data security, it is required that interviewers and the fieldwork organisation take care to use only secure internet connections to upload the data collected to the server (avoiding public Wi-Fi internet connections).

2.7. Data Protection, Consent and Data Linkage

Data protection

The GGS fieldwork operation model and data management plan have been approved by the GGP Ethics Board and the KNAW Data Protection Officer and conform to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). At the country level, national teams should make sure that their operations also comply with the regulations of their own institution and country.

Consent

Data can be only collected from respondents who explicitly consent to participation in the survey. All respondents are presented with the same introductory text at the beginning of the interview. This repeats some of the information that is stated in the original invitation letter as well as asserting that respondents should be alone, if possible, to prevent interference. They will also be provided with information on whom to contact should they have any questions. Respondents who have had a F2F interview might be left with a contact card by the interviewer in case they have further questions later.

Introductory Text:

This survey is about family, work and everyday life. Your answers will help us understand the complexities of today's families and the reality of people at different stages of their life. Our aim is to better understand, for example, what influences people's decision to have children or how they share household chores in couples. The results will be used to advise policy-makers on how to improve issues such as work-life balance, social relationships between generations and gender equality. Your participation is voluntary. If you don't want to answer any of the questions as some of them deal with sensitive topics, you are free to skip these at any point by choosing the response option 'refuse'. We will remove all personal identifiers from the data and ensure that your answers are only accessed by authorised and verified researchers for scientific purposes.

Closing Text:

Many thanks for your participation in the survey, we greatly appreciate your time. If you have any questions about the survey or would like further information, you can contact us on [TELEPHONE NUMBER] or by emailing [EMAIL ADDRESS].

Respondents should be also separately asked if the fieldwork agency can store their data so that they can be contacted for the next round of the wave of the survey.

Data linkage

Administrative registers include data for the total population, both on events (e.g. births, moves) and on status (e.g. marital status, educational attainment) at certain time points. The incorporation of administrative data, along with other types of data, into social survey programmes has demonstrated significant benefits not only from a substantive point of view but also from a methodological perspective. Another important reason for linking interview data with administrative records is to save interviewing time. So far, the most comprehensive use of population registers is done in the Nordic countries. Countries with robust administrative records can integrate data from survey interviews and registers, enabling them to draw register-based samples. The GGP has already implemented some successful initiatives linking survey microdata and administrative records.

There are two different types of data linkages that may be considered:

- Administrative data may be used to pre-fill the survey questionnaire, thus avoiding to ask respondents about information that is already available from other sources. However, when doing this, national teams should ensure that this information from external sources will be possible to include in the final dataset and be released to the GGP User community.
- Alternatively, linkages to administrative data can be done after the fieldwork, for example, to enhance information on the survey respondents.

In both cases, explicit consent should be asked by elaborating on and specifying the introductory text.

The integration of administrative data linkage should be considered by all national teams and discussed with the GGP CCT at the outset of the project.

2.8. Incentives

Considerable attention has been given in survey methodology to incentives and the role they play in achieving higher cooperation from survey respondents. It is clear from existing research that the use of incentives is desirable or even essential (especially in some Western European countries) given several positive effects: in particular, increasing time and cost-efficiency (increasing 'early' responses and decreasing the need for additional contacts). When a person receives the invitation to participate and an incentive is already included (or mentioned in case it is a conditional incentive) which is seen as a 'goodwill gesture' that can help build trust between the survey data collector/national team and the respondent. This in turn has the potential to encourage compliance with the request to complete the survey.

Considering the crucial role of the national context in defining an effective strategy for providing incentives (or even whether incentives are culturally appropriate), the ultimate decision rests with the national team. However, it should be kept in mind that, in general, incentives should be presented as a token of appreciation for participating in the survey, not as payment for the response. The amount of the incentive should be reasonable, avoiding any amount that might raise suspicion about the researcher's or organisation's motives. In addition, it is important to convey to potential respondents that the data collected will be analysed by researchers studying changes in society. The scientific findings will provide important insights for policy-makers on pressing societal challenges.

2.9. Tendering Specifications for Fieldwork Agency

The fieldwork agency contracted to field the GGS should:

- have experience in fielding nationwide surveys based on probability samples;
- be able to construct probability-based sample of individuals or of addresses representative for the target population (i.e., be able to draw the sample from registers, if possible);
- have appropriate fieldwork management system that can be used to manage fieldwork operations and support survey software;
- be able to send advance letters and reminders to the respondents, using different types of communication channels (regular post, email, phone messages);
- in case of CAPI, have a high enough number of interviewers experienced in conducting F2F surveys;
- in case of CAPI, have a high enough number of portable devices (tablets/laptops) that can be used to collect the data during interviews;
- adhere to the ICC/ESOMAR International Code on Market, Opinion and Social Research and Data Analytics⁵.

⁵ <https://esomar.org/code-and-guidelines/icc-esomar-code>.

2.10. Panel Maintenance Strategies

The GGS consists of a baseline survey as well as one or two follow-up questionnaires (three and six years later respectively). It is essential for national teams to already plan and budget appropriate panel maintenance strategies.

There is an extensive list of reasons why someone chooses (or not) to respond to a survey and a host of external factors that may influence them towards a decision regarding continuing to participate in subsequent waves of the study in the case of longitudinal surveys. In the GGS, as in other longitudinal studies, one of the fieldwork challenges is to be able to trace and contact all respondents after 3 years (the time between GGS waves). This requires measures to trace and motivate panel members in the period between waves.

Panel attrition occurs when respondents drop out of a panel study. Attrition is usually rather high between the first and the second wave and comparatively low between later panel waves. It is recommended that the maximum attrition rate is lower than 20% after first wave. Attrition can be due to no contact, or no cooperation because the person is not able or refuses to continue to participate in the study. Longitudinal survey data is used to analyse the causes and consequences of demographic change and other social phenomena. Therefore, panel attrition has important negative consequences given the objectives and research focus of most researchers using this type of data

Achieving high response rates and low levels of attrition is one of the key challenges for longitudinal social surveys. The fieldwork organisation has several key tasks in the efforts to reduce panel attrition: to locate and contact the respondent; to cooperate with her/ him; to trace respondents moving between survey waves. These tasks vary in the first and consecutive waves and also by mode of data collection. In the initial wave, the primary focus is to locate and contact the respondents, while in subsequent waves the emphasis shifts to tracing respondents who may have relocated between waves (relevant especially for CAWI).

The GGP has, since the first round of data collection, devoted efforts to minimise attrition. The four key recommendations for fieldwork organisations are:

- continuous and close cooperation between the research institute, the fieldwork agency, the interviewers and the respondents;
- well-written and formatted invitation letters, websites and other channels of communication;
- incentives for respondents that can vary across countries;
- regular contact (ideally bi-annual) with respondents through letters, information brochures, requests for updated contact information, and where feasible, the collection of annual information via a short questionnaire.

This list of recommendations is not exhaustive, and the national team and fieldwork organisation are encouraged to reflect on further measures that might work well and be suited to the national context. Panel maintenance should be included as a budgetary item within all grant applications and explicitly delegated as a responsibility to a member of the national team. The GGP CCT should be notified of the identity of this individual.

3. PREPARATION

3.1. Translation & National Adaptation

The translation process plays a very important role in cross-national surveys. Equivalence in survey translation requires that respondents understand survey questions in the same way across languages and express themselves in the same way (i.e., the same attitude should correspond to the same observed answer). A good survey translation endeavours to attain conceptual, linguistic and semantic accuracy.

For cross-national research to be effective, it is essential that the measurement instruments used across populations are comparable. This implies that the data obtained in different countries should consistently represent the same concepts they intend to measure across the respondents. If there are inadequately translated questions, the whole project suffers as data comparability is greatly affected.

The GGP requires that national teams use TranslationCTRL for the translation of the GGS questionnaire. The TranslationCTRL is a web-based tool, initially developed for SHARE, specially designed to allow translators to translate questionnaires without the burden of understanding complex routing and programming codes for large multi-lingual questionnaires. It has been used in several large international studies. The TranslationCTRL offers additional benefits such as its ability to document diverse translation steps and communication processes. It also has an export functionality that allows for an equivalent bilingual display of translated questionnaires alongside the master questionnaire which is a beneficial feature for data archives, data users and subsequent waves of the GGP.

Translators should keep in mind that the GGS questionnaire is complex and some of the concepts might not be easily translated into the target language. We highly recommend translators and reviewers add comments to their translations in TranslationCTRL when they are in doubt or run into problems with the translation. It is not mandatory that the translation or review is done by professional translators. However, it is essential that individuals involved in the translation and review have a very high proficiency in English and are native speakers in the target language. It is highly recommended to work in teams so that alternative options for translation can be discussed. Furthermore, some expertise in social science survey research is necessary to understand the concepts that a given formulation is intended to measure. During translation, care should be taken to align the translations with existing translations including previous translations with the previous round of the GGS.

Information from the TranslationCTRL database can be automatically imported into source code. Alternatively, it can be exported into other formats like Excel, Word, DDI, and GetText, making it easy to integrate into a wide range of other survey development processes. Since its first release in 2004, the TranslationCTRL has been under continuous development. It has proven itself a good system for managing multilingual questionnaire translation projects over the web.

3.2. Pre-testing

The main objectives of the pre-testing are identifying and fixing problems experienced by interviewers and respondents. The pre-testing will encompass both the testing of the questionnaire

and the technical pre-testing of the questionnaire programming, devices and server connection. This is crucial to meet and ensure the data quality standards of the GGS.

Pre-testing of the questionnaire

At its core, pre-testing is designed to make sure that people understand the questions (wording and translations) and are presented with adequate response options. While pilot and even full-scale surveys may be outsourced, we strongly recommend that at least one testing phase is handled by the members of the national team in order to develop and fine-tune the overall survey. National team members have reliable knowledge of the language, as well as the cultural and cognitive skills needed to answer the questions.

Testing phases take time. Along with the translation phase, they are the most time-consuming component of survey preparation. They may take several weeks or months, depending on the project (survey conducted in one or many languages, experience and size of the testing team, etc.). Pre-testing is an indispensable stage that must be planned for and adequately budgeted.

Pre-tests should be done in several stages with an eye on various elements. The first thing is to test to make sure that the translation is fine and that there are no errors in the questions and answer categories. A trained tester or interviewer can often identify a confusing question in a way that not even data analysis would show. Testers may administer the questionnaire among themselves or engage in fictional scenarios such as multiple family scenarios or pre-prepared mock interviews.

Further along in the questionnaire formalisation process, the interviewers (if CAPI) must be brought in. There are various testing and validation methods, and several tests may be necessary, depending on the types of modification made (reformulation of translations, changes to the list of response categories, etc.). The tests are also an opportunity to develop, clarify or improve interviewer training, another crucial factor in data quality.

Technical pre-testing

All countries will work with the same common digital version of the questionnaire, programmed and provided centrally by the GGP CCT. The key reasons for doing this are:

- to ensure that the questionnaire is administered in the same way across countries (eliminating the need for post-harmonisation);
- to make sure that GGS data can be prepared for data release quickly and efficiently;
- to better monitor fieldwork in each country.

The digital questionnaire, programmed in Blaise, will be tested in the national language(s). The GGP CCT covers Blaise software licensing costs (fieldwork agencies are not required to have Blaise licenses).

As part of the pre-testing phase, the GGP CCT will conduct a series of technical checks in order to make sure that the questionnaire does not have any problems in terms of routing or layout. Additional checks will be conducted to verify the functioning of the Blaise software and communication with the server.

Pre-testing in CAPI mode

The fieldwork agency conducts the pre-test according to the following specifications:

- The pre-test has to include at least 30 participants. The sampling and recruitment of the participants will be left to the fieldwork agency but ideally should represent approximately the characteristics of the population of interest.
- For the pre-test, the fieldwork agency will provide the interviewers with the devices they will be using during fieldwork.
- The fieldwork agency needs to take note and report:
 - any problems that occur with the understanding of the translation of the questionnaire and on which items;
 - any technical problems that occur with the questionnaire-environment interface;
 - any problems that occur with the display and interaction with the questionnaire in the agency's devices;
 - any technical problems that occur with the upload and transmission of the data to NIDI servers.
- Regarding technical issues, it is essential to note and report any problems that the interviewers might experience regarding the device and software (e.g., filling in and uploading the contact form, interacting with the data entry interface, uploading, etc.).
- At the end of the pre-test, the fieldwork agency provides a short and informal report in English regarding the results of the pre-test.

Based on the above report, the GGP CCT, national team and fieldwork agency will discuss any issues and implement necessary measures to enable the successful completion of the fieldwork. **After this stage, the GGP CCT will lock the questionnaire which means that no further changes will be made to the survey instrument.** If errors are spotted after this point, they cannot be fixed.

3.3. Interviewer Training for CAPI Mode

Although the interviewer training can be country-specific, some parts of the training program can be standardised in order to maintain the comparability of different fieldwork procedures. The proposed standardisation of the interviewer training mainly focuses on the interviewer's conduct, presentation of the survey and some interviewer techniques such as rules for survey question presentation and probing techniques. If experienced interviewers are assigned to the survey, some of the points outlined may already be well known.

GGP CCT will assist national teams in conducting the interviewer training, providing all necessary resources and knowledge. Additionally, the train-the-trainers sessions will be organised.

3.4. Information Material for Respondents

A survey can be a powerful tool for gathering information. However, ensuring that people participate in a survey is an important aspect that should not be overlooked. If we cannot convince them to answer the questions, then the survey will have limited value.

In particular, and in the context of rapidly declining response rates in many countries (observed for all social science surveys), it is important to motivate participants and to improve the respondent experience. Additionally, for a CAWI survey without an interviewer present, the questionnaire remains the only means of communication between the survey researchers and the respondents. Therefore, all the small encouragements an interviewer might once have given the respondent need now be present in a script. Successful respondent relations are the key to getting people to cooperate with survey invitations and obtaining (accurate) data.

Invitation letters

The invitation letter (also known as an advance letter) provides a brief overview of the survey, and explains why a household or particular person (depending on the sampling frame) was selected and what to expect as a survey participant. In each country fielding the GGS, selected (potential) participants always receive a written invitation (a letter by postal mail, an email or SMS). The invitation letter should be prepared by the national team.

The invitation always names the survey organisation that will be conducting the fieldwork (including information on how to contact their offices) and interviewers must always carry credentials with them.

The main aim of the written invitation is to inform the respondent, stress the importance of his/her participation and inform him/her of the rights as a participant in the survey. In the case of CAWI, the participants receive instructions on how to access the questionnaire and the timeframe in which to do so.

In the case of CAPI, the potential respondent is notified that the interviewer will attempt to contact the household following the receipt of the written invitation. The respondent is then free to make the most suitable arrangement with the interviewer and schedule a visit when the interview would be carried out.

While the GGP is quite flexible with regards to the format and look and feel of the invitation letter (logos, colours, A4), the content should detail:

- the purpose for which the data is being collected and topics covered in the questionnaire, including the fact that the questionnaire covers sensitive topics;
- the voluntary nature of the research and possibility of withdrawing from the study, as well as the right not to answer specific questions;
- who will be given access to the de-personalised GGS datasets and for what purposes;
- who coordinates the study at the international and national levels (and contact details);
- who will use the data;
- the respondent's unique access code;

- the link to the GGS or landing page (for CAWI mode);
- for household or address based sample frames, who should be completing the survey (e.g. next birthday method).

For a GGS that is carried out in multiple languages, please keep in mind that the respondent letter should be translated and offered in these same multiple languages.

Participation incentives

The decision to use incentives for respondents is made by national teams in collaboration with fieldwork agencies and can vary across countries. The key reason for this has to do with the suitability (or not) to use monetary or other incentives at the national level.

Participants should be informed about the incentive in the initial written invitation that they receive or, in some cases, the interviewers will mention and provide the incentive when the appointment for the face-to-face interview takes place. In case the participant has questions about the incentive, interviewers are trained to explain the purpose of the incentive.

Landing page

The invitation letter contains the URL that directs individuals to a country-specific landing page with information about the study, how data is processed and who to contact with further questions. A template for this landing page is available on the GGP website and it can be translated and adapted for national-level contexts.

The GGP CCT will prepare the landing page. National teams are expected to provide the content, as well as logos that will appear on the landing page.

Frequently asked questions

It is no surprise that selected households and respondents will have questions about the GGS as well as about the organisations listed in the invitation letters. While the letter does specify contacts, often the respondents need a simpler way to find the information they are looking for. A frequently asked questions or FAQ page is a place for visitors to easily find answers to their questions in one place.

There are many benefits to having a well-crafted FAQ page or section that answers specific questions about your product or business. It can;

- establish trust by showing respondents the legitimacy of the survey;
- save you time and money by reducing the number of repetitive calls and emails to your help desk or support staff;
- convert selected visitors into actual survey participants.

Often respondents have general questions about the survey (who is funding the survey? how were they selected? where did we get their address?) or concerns (how will their data be kept confidential? why is it necessary to perform data linkage? why do we ask about fertility intentions or other more

sensitive topics?). Similar to a FAQ page, survey agencies direct respondents to an “Information for Survey Participants” page where many details of the survey are outlined.

The GGP webpage has an informative section answering frequently asked questions from survey participants⁶. The GGP has also produced a short animated video to inform non-academic audiences about how the GGP works to improve policy and society⁷.

Other respondent materials

There are many ways to engage respondents, each involving an investment in money, time and effort. The efficiency of methods can highly depend on budget and national context.

One approach is sharing information with respondents where brochures and factsheets containing interesting facts and additional survey-related content can be provided along with the invitation or reminder letter or on the survey’s website.

Another strategy involves utilising social media platforms, such as Facebook or Twitter, or traditional channels like radio announcements and newspaper ads, to promote the survey and encourage participation.

3.5. Sample Management and Contact History

Contact information for CAPI

All the information relating to the contacts attempted should be thoroughly documented in a standardised way. In the GGS, the way of recording such information is in a contact form (paper or electronic) completed by the interviewer after each contact attempt. The contact form data also helps the interviewer in planning her/ his fieldwork activities. This data is personal and includes names and addresses and is always held and managed by the national team. **The GGP CCT does not have access to this data and if fieldwork reporting is shared with the GGP CCT, all personal identifiers have to be deleted.**

The contact form has additional functionalities. It represents precious data on the fieldwork process itself. The form is also an essential piece of information for tracking purposes between the waves of the panel since it contains a lot of information that can be used for more effective tracking.

The initial sections of the contact form are meant for the identification of the respondent and interviewer (through the identification codes). In the case of the household and address-based samples, the selected person’s full name should also be recorded. Important additional information includes the selected person’s telephone number and e-mail which will also enable any potential re-contact. The provided phone number and e-mail helps the interviewer to re-contact the individual, make or change an appointment or in any other possible cases where the contact is needed. If the target person is not present or refuses to participate, the refusal or absence should also be recorded.

⁶ <https://www.ggp-i.org/participants>

⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ODuwyJdC4HE&t=3s>

Each contact attempt should be documented in detail. The times and dates of each contact are recorded. The type of contact should be recorded as well as its outcome. If the contact attempt was not successful, an explanation should be given as to why. If the address was not traceable or occupied, it should also be indicated. In the case of the contact person not being the target person, it has to be recorded as such and distinguished at least among: a resident household/family member, a non-resident family/visitor/friend, a neighbour, or a building manager/ security guard/ or another gatekeeper. In the case of the outcome of the contact being a refusal, a reason should be specified as to why the contacted person refused. Upon refusal, the interviewer can also be asked to provide a subjective assessment of likelihood of future cooperation. This estimation is useful to help the fieldwork agency decide whether to re-issue the case, and to help any future interviewer. In the case of a non-contact, some additional information could be sought with the neighbours and recorded on the form for future reference.

The contact form should at least contain the following mandatory fields:

- Interviewer ID
- Address ID
- Respondent ID
- Address (road, house no. & town)
- Personal contacts (e-mail and phone number) if provided
- Visit no. (number of the contact attempt at the address)
- Date and time
- Outcome of the contact:
 - Contact and appointment scheduled
 - Contact and interview
 - No contact
 - Hard refusal (classified as 'hard refusal' if the respondent says "*I don't want to participate*", "*please do not contact me again*", "*remove me from your list*", no further attempts are made)
 - Soft refusal (the classification of 'soft refusal' is used when the respondent says "*no time now*", "*I am busy*", "*can you come another time*", "*I don't know*", etc. Two further contact attempts are made and if the respondent still offers a soft refusal the contact attempt is set to refusal)
 - Out-of-scope/ Ineligible
 - Other non-interview (for e.g., has health problems; language difficulties: does not speak the language of the GGS questionnaire; temporarily absent during the entire survey period; death; emigrated)
- If refusal, annotate the reason provided
- Other observations

The decision on the choice of software to be used for the managing and recording of the contact attempts is left to the fieldwork agency. The fieldwork agency will maintain a database in which a log is kept of fieldwork efforts, where all contact attempts are recorded.

Contact information in CAWI

In CAWI mode, contact information is also important. This should include information such as:

- When was the first invitation letter sent.
- Was this letter sent via regular post, by email or in the form of text message.
- If the letter was sent to a specific person (in the case of individual-based sampling frame) or a household name, or generic (to a resident of this address).
- When were reminders sent, by which means and how many. Were they addressed to all non-response or targeted to those who have ever logged in.

4. FIELDWORK AND REPORTING

4.1. Fieldwork and Monitoring

CAPI and fieldwork monitoring

During fieldwork both the GGP CCT and the fieldwork agency will closely monitor the fieldwork activities. Blaise collects a large amount of paradata from each interviewer which logs each keystroke for every interview. Using this data, the GGP CCT assess whether interviewers are completing the interviews accurately and whether protocols are in place to identify issues such as straight-lining and technical issues.

Another important aspect that will be assessed is the coverage among the entire sample, providing an early indication of any difficulties across subgroups (for example, it is common during fieldwork that women and older people are easier to contact). Another aspect associated with the evaluation of data quality is the prevalence of item non-response. High item non-response can be an indication of unwillingness to participate or inconvenience. Also, the number of previous partners and the total number of children are vital parts of the GGS and it is crucial that they are measured correctly. For example, problems can arise when there is a failure to record previous relationships, which might drag down the number of children recorded given that the number of previous partners and number of children are closely interlinked. Interviewers should be clear in their explanation of what counts as a previous relationship and ask respondents to affirm their answers.

In addition, the interviewer evaluations at the end of the face-to-face interview will be used to assess if there were any interruptions during the interviews, if the respondents were influenced by anyone present and to evaluate the perceived quality of the collected information. **The GGP CCT will report on a regular basis to the fieldwork agency and will provide advice and recommendations for fieldwork improvement.**

CAWI and fieldwork monitoring

On a regular basis, the GGP CCT provides the national team with a list of all respondent IDs that have completed or partially completed the survey and from this, the national team can issue the necessary reminders. The GGP recommends issuing at least three reminders a week apart. Where possible the mode of the reminder should be varied (i.e. letter, phone, email). At the end of the fieldwork period, the national team can follow up non-respondents with the possibility of a face-to-face interview but national teams should be advised that these re-contact attempts are costly and provide limited additional coverage of the target sample.

5. DATA PROCESSING, DOCUMENTATION, ARCHIVING AND DISSEMINATION

The GGP CCT aims to release the data as rapidly as possible for users. This involves various steps including data processing, calculation of weights, data documentation, data archiving and data release.

5.1. Data Processing

In the data processing phase, the GGP CCT will;

- label all variables and values in English and check that all variables and values labels are the same across countries;
- code country-specific response categories;
- code country-specific questions and place them at the end of the data file;
- correct country and occupation information if needed and add ISO / ISCO codes;
- remove all names and pseudonyms used in the Life History section of the questionnaire.

In the case of a web survey, the GGP CCT will in addition:

- delete cases that dropped off before they reached the end of section LHI (Life History Section);
- add missing values for variables that respondents did not reach because they dropped out in sections after LHI;
- drop cases that have a very high number of missing information on their responses.

In the case of a pilot, the GGP CCT will:

- label all variables and values in English;
- correct country and occupation information if needed and add ISO / ISCO codes;
- remove all names and pseudonyms used in the Life History section of the questionnaire;
- prepare – with help of the national team – a text document that is released together with the dataset. This document includes information about: the aim of the pilot, if the pilot is based on a representative sample or not, information on how to cite the data, and any other information that is useful for researchers using the pilot data.

Harmonised Histories

The GGP CCT also creates a Harmonised Histories dataset based on the cleaned micro-data file. The preparation of this dataset allows for logical and substantive checks to improve the quality of the GGS data. The Harmonised Histories is an international comparative dataset, created through harmonising data from the GGS and other surveys into one common format. The aim of the Harmonised Histories is to facilitate cross-national research on topics related to transition to adulthood, family formation, and non-marital childbearing. The dataset focuses on fertility and

partnership histories, organised in a way that makes it well-suited for event history analysis. In addition, it captures socio-economic status, place of residence, information on the childhood family (e.g. parental divorce, number of siblings), etc. Further information about the Harmonised Histories information including data manuals and information on how to access the data is available on GGP's website⁸.

5.2. Data Documentation and Metadata

The GGP CCT is responsible for documenting the data. However, this is done based on the information provided by the national teams. To gather this information the GGP CCT will share a questionnaire with the national team at the end of fieldwork. The national team is asked to provide information according to the DDI standard⁹ about the following topics:

- Study description (e.g. contributors to the data collection).
- Related materials (e.g. invitation letters, webpages).
- Coverage (e.g., geographical and demographic coverage of the sample).
- Funding.
- Data collection (mode, interviewer training, contact protocols, weighting).
- Methodology (sampling strategy, non-response rates).

5.3. Calculation of Weights

GGP CCT will calculate design (if applicable) and post-stratification weights. To implement the weights in the dataset, the national team is asked to provide information on the following issues:

- For all respondents in the dataset, the probability of inclusion into the sample for the respective respondent, stratum to which the respondent belongs (for stratified samples) and sampling unit(s) to which the respondent belongs (for clustered samples).
- Population figures on five variables of interest: age, gender, region, level of education and marital status.

5.4. Data Archiving and Data Access

Data Archiving

The GGP CCT is responsible for the preservation and long-term availability of the GGS data. The data stored by the GGP is sensitive and depersonalised, but not anonymised. The reason for this has to do with the level of detail of the microdata collected, i.e. if a respondent has very particular

⁸ <https://www.ggp-i.org/data/harmonised-histories/>

⁹ The Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) is the international standard for data documentation in social sciences. DDI is recommended by CESSDA (the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archive) and is utilised by the most widely used software and technologies in social sciences.

characteristics and/ or history and lives in a scarcely populated area, there is the remote possibility that a data user can suspect who the respondent is.

In the case of CAPI, it is important that interviewers are prepared to explain that the information collected will remain confidential, no individual names will be used for any purpose and that all information will be pooled for statistical analyses.

During the fieldwork the data is collected and stored on a server that is owned and operated by the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences (KNAW). The KNAW does not have access to personal identifiers at any stage and these are held securely and independently in the fieldwork country for the purposes of re-contacting respondents in subsequent waves.

The data will remain usable indefinitely unless a respondent contacts the national team and requests that their data be deleted. If such a request is made, the national team must provide the GGP CCT with the respondent ID number for these individuals and the GGP CCT will then erase all data for these individuals.

Access to the microdata

The microdata is available to the GGP Research Community and the files are available free of charge for approved researchers. The applicants need to apply for access through the GGP website: the applicant creates a user account with basic information (used to check the legitimacy of the applicant) and accepts the “Statement of affiliation, confidentiality and acceptable usage for GGS datasets”. The applications are processed by the CCT with the support of UNECE. The UNECE provides this service as a contribution to the GGP, of which it was a founder member. The CCT will review the application by checking for incorrectly filled-in fields while the UNECE will check the validity of the research institute. After the verification and acceptance of the request, the applicant has access to the anonymous microdata through the user account and can download the file in Stata, SPSS, and CSV format.

GGG Metadata

GGP uses the software *Colectica* to convert files exported from Blaise into files compliant with the DDI structure, thus ensuring that all fieldwork metadata is preserved throughout the data lifecycle. This lifecycle approach allows for versioning to be managed across the data lifecycle.

Naming conventions and keyword search are adopted in line with standards in the social science research infrastructures. The GGP works closely with other research infrastructures to develop and apply such standards. The GGP uses a two-level versioning approach (x.y) by which an increase in the first level (x) indicates a major change to the data. An increase in the second level (y) indicates to researchers that there have been non-critical amendments and updates to the data. Researchers can examine the versioning documentation to assess whether they need to use the newer version of the data.

While browsing the data online¹⁰, users can find information about the fieldwork metadata provided by national teams as well as distributors, keywords, abstract, and guidelines on bibliographic citation.

¹⁰ <https://ggp.colectica.org>.

This documentation and processing are conducted at no cost to the national team and is wholly the responsibility of the GGP CCT.

5.5. Publicity and Dissemination

The GGP actively promotes and disseminates studies and initiatives based on GGS data via the GGP webpage, monthly GGP-connect webinars, a bi-monthly newsletter and through social media. A GGP bibliography is openly available also via the GGP webpage with information on publications using GGS data.

National teams are also encouraged to have their own dissemination activities.

Colophon:

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